

Output-only discovery of stochastic dynamics in moment space

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Abstract

Discovering governing equations of stochastic dynamical systems directly from data remains challenging when stochastic excitations are unobserved and measurements are limited. Existing data-driven approaches either treat stochasticity as measurement noise or rely on high-dimensional probability-density formulations that are computationally difficult to apply in practice. Here, we introduce an output-only framework for discovering nonlinear stochastic differential equations directly from response data by operating in moment space rather than state space. The proposed approach represents drift and diffusion terms as sparse combinations of candidate nonlinear functions and identifies the governing equations through sparse regression on deterministic moment equations derived from stochastic dynamics. Because the formulation evolves implicitly with respect to stochastic forcing, the method enables direct identification of stochastic systems without requiring excitation measurements. To enable robust inference under realistic data limitations, we further develop Selective Segmented Sampling and Moment Aggregation strategies for estimating transient conditional moments from comparatively short stochastic signals. The framework accurately recovers both deterministic and stochastic components of representative nonlinear systems, including stochastic Duffing, van der Pol, Lorenz, and Mathieu systems, demonstrating applicability to multistable, self-excited, chaotic, and multiplicative-noise dynamics even under strong stochastic forcing and limited-data conditions. By combining moment equations with sparse model discovery, the present work establishes a low-dimensional framework for output-only discovery of stochastic dynamics from limited measurements.

Keywords: nonlinear stochastic modeling | stochastic differential equation | moment equations | sparse nonlinear regression | system identification

Significance

Many real-world systems, from turbulent structures to biological processes and financial markets, evolve under the combined effects of nonlinear dynamics and randomness. Discovering the governing equations of such systems directly from data is challenging, particularly when the random excitations cannot be measured. We introduce a framework that identifies stochastic dynamical equations using only observed responses by combining statistical moment equations with sparse data-driven model discovery. The method further incorporates data-efficient estimation strategies that substantially reduce measurement requirements. This approach enables practical discovery of stochastic systems from limited observations and may benefit applications across engineering, physics, and other data-driven sciences.

Nonlinear stochastic dynamics arise ubiquitously across natural sciences, engineering, and socio-economic systems, where random fluctuations fundamentally influence system evolution rather than merely corrupting observations [1]. Representative examples include Brownian motion driven by molecular collisions [2], civil structures subjected to turbulent wind and seismic excitations [3], tumor growth mediated by stochastic immune interactions, and fluctuations in financial markets [4]. Such systems are naturally described by stochastic differential equations (SDEs) [5], in which deterministic drift mechanisms coexist with stochastic forcing. Although these governing equations are traditionally derived from first principles, many real-world systems remain only partially understood or are prohibitively complex due to unresolved multiscale interactions [6], motivating data-driven approaches that infer governing dynamics directly from observations [7].

Recent advances in high-performance computing and machine learning [8, 9] have significantly accelerated progress in data-driven discovery of nonlinear dynamical systems [10, 11]. In particular, the Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics (SINDy) framework demonstrated that many deterministic systems can be represented parsimoniously using sparse combinations of candidate nonlinear functions [12]. Numerous extensions have since improved robustness to noise, incorporated control inputs, and identified partial differential equations [13, 1, 14, 15]. Despite these advances, most existing methods remain fundamentally designed for deterministic systems.

Identifying stochastic dynamics directly from data remains considerably more challenging. A common approximation treats stochasticity as measurement noise superimposed on deterministic dynamics, which becomes inadequate when random fluctuations actively shape the system evolution or when multiplicative noise is present [16]. Alternative approaches infer the associated Fokker-Planck equation governing probability density evolution, often through Kramers-Moyal expansions or related operator-theoretic formulations [17, 6, 18, 19]. Although theoretically appealing, these methods typically require extensive ensemble sampling and high-dimensional probability density estimation, resulting in substantial computational challenges [1, 20]. Consequently, a gap persists between methods that identify SDEs but require direct excitation measurements and output-only approaches that operate in prohibitively high-dimensional spaces.

Moment equations provide a natural intermediate representation between stochastic trajectories and full probability density evolution [21, 22, 23]. Instead of resolving the complete probability distribution, moment equations describe the evolution of low-order statistical moments through a hierarchy of deterministic ordinary differential equations [24]. These equations can be derived either from Itô calculus applied directly to SDEs or from integral transforms of the associated Fokker-Planck equation [25, 26, 27]. Since moment dynamics evolve implicitly with respect to stochastic excitations, they offer a low-dimensional deterministic representation that retains essential stochastic information while avoiding the curse of dimensionality associated with probability density formulations. This perspective suggests the possibility of performing stochastic system discovery directly in moment space using response measurements alone.

Here, we introduce an output-only framework for discovering nonlinear stochastic differential equations directly from limited response data. The drift and diffusion terms of the governing SDE are represented sparsely using candidate nonlinear libraries, while the identification is performed by minimizing discrepancies between predicted and observed time derivatives of statistical moments. To enable robust moment estimation under realistic data limitations, we further develop a Selective Segmented Sampling (SSS) strategy together with a Moment Aggregation (MA) approach that extracts transient statistical information from comparatively short stochastic signals. The proposed framework accurately recovers nonlinear stochastic dynamics from response-only measurements, including systems with strong stochastic forcing and limited available data, thereby establishing a low-dimensional approach for output-only stochastic system discovery.

Moment-space framework for stochastic discovery

We consider nonlinear stochastic dynamical systems governed by Langevin-type stochastic differential equations (SDEs) [25, 26] of the form

$$d\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})dt + \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x})d\mathbf{w}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(t)$ denotes the system states, $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$ represents the deterministic *drift* dynamics, and the *diffusion* term $\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x})d\mathbf{w}$ describes stochastic forcing through independent Wiener processes $\mathbf{w}(t)$. Constant diffusion coefficients correspond to additive noise, whereas state-dependent diffusion terms enable multiplicative stochasticity.

Once the governing SDE is specified, the corresponding hierarchy of moment equations can be derived from either Itô calculus or the associated Fokker-Planck equation [21, 27] (*SI Appendix, section 2.3*). For a prescribed truncation order s , the resulting dynamics take the general form

$$\dot{\mathbf{m}}_L = \mathbf{P}_1\mathbf{m}_L + \mathbf{P}_2\mathbf{m}_H + \mathbf{Q}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{m}_L collects low-order response moments up to order s , while \mathbf{m}_H contains higher-order moments arising from nonlinear interactions. The coefficient matrices \mathbf{P}_1 , \mathbf{P}_2 , and vector \mathbf{Q} are determined by the drift and diffusion functions $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x})$. Unlike the high-dimensional FPK equation, Eq. 2 constitutes a low-dimensional deterministic system describing the evolution of statistical moments of the stochastic response.

To enable parsimonious system discovery, the drift and diffusion functions are represented as sparse combinations of candidate nonlinear basis functions [12, 28],

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \boldsymbol{\Xi}_f\boldsymbol{\Theta}_f(\mathbf{x}), \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}) = \boldsymbol{\Xi}_\sigma\boldsymbol{\Theta}_\sigma(\mathbf{x}), \quad (3)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Theta}_f$ and $\boldsymbol{\Theta}_\sigma$ denote libraries of candidate nonlinear functions, and $\boldsymbol{\Xi}_f$, $\boldsymbol{\Xi}_\sigma$ are sparse coefficient matrices to be identified. Polynomial libraries are employed in the present work, e.g., for a two-state SDE, they may be constructed as

$$\boldsymbol{\Theta}_g(\mathbf{x}) = [1 \quad x_1 \quad x_2 \quad x_1^2 \quad x_1x_2 \quad x_2^2 \quad \dots]^T,$$

where the subscript $g \in \{\mathbf{f}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}\}$.

The identification is performed by minimizing discrepancies between predicted and observed time derivatives of statistical moments. Moment trajectories estimated from response measurements are assembled into a data matrix $\mathbf{M}_L = [\mathbf{m}_L(t_1) \quad \mathbf{m}_L(t_2) \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{m}_L(t_m)]$. Observed moment derivatives $\dot{\mathbf{M}}_L$ are obtained by numerically differentiating \mathbf{M}_L in time, while the predicted moment derivatives are obtained from Eq. 2 using the sparse representations in Eq. 3. The governing equations are identified by minimizing

$$L(\boldsymbol{\Xi}_f, \boldsymbol{\Xi}_\sigma) = \|\mathbf{P}_1\mathbf{M}_L + \mathbf{P}_2\mathbf{M}_H + \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{I}_m - \dot{\mathbf{M}}_L\|_F^2, \quad (4)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_F$ is the Frobenius norm. Because the diffusion terms enter the moment equations through quadratic variations of Wiener processes, the resulting optimization problem becomes nonconvex in the diffusion coefficients. Sparse nonlinear regression is then employed to identify parsimonious governing equations corresponding to the minimum loss [12, 18, 6]. A two-phase sparse nonlinear regression algorithm developed to address the resulting nonconvex optimization problem is described in *SI Appendix, section 3.3*. For systems with multiplicative noise, additional non-uniqueness issues may arise due to the statistical

Figure 1: Output-only stochastic system discovery in moment space. A moderately long response-only signal is converted into transient statistical moments using Selective Segmented Sampling (SSS) (see Figure 2). Sparse representations of the drift and diffusion functions are embedded into deterministic moment equations, and the governing stochastic differential equations are identified by sparse nonlinear regression on moment derivatives.

equivalence of certain diffusion representations. These effects are illustrated for stochastic Mathieu systems and discussed further in *SI Appendix, sections 4.4 and 5*.

The overall framework is summarized schematically in Figure 1. A moderately long sample of the response signal is first converted into transient statistical moments $\mathbf{m}_L(t)$ and $\mathbf{m}_H(t)$ using the proposed Selective Segmented Sampling strategy (*SI Appendix, section 3.4*). Sparse representations of the drift and diffusion functions are subsequently embedded into the moment equations, and the governing stochastic dynamics are finally identified through sparse regression on moment derivatives.

Transient moment estimation from limited data

The proposed identification framework relies on transient statistical moments as input data. In principle, these moments could be estimated from large ensembles of trajectories initialized from identical conditions, analogous to Monte Carlo simulation. Such an approach, however, is rarely practical in experiments and field measurements, where repeated realizations are costly and prescribed initial conditions are difficult to enforce. Consequently, a central challenge in this moment-based stochastic discovery is the estimation of reliable transient moments from limited response measurements, ideally from a single moderately long sample of the response signal.

To overcome these limitations, we introduce a Selective Segmented Sampling (SSS) strategy for contributing to extract transient moments from a single, moderately long, sample of the response signal ((a) in Figure 2). The measured signal is first subdivided into multiple segments longer than the characteristic re -

Figure 2: Transient moment estimation from limited response data. (Top) Selective Segmented Sampling (SSS) extracts transient statistical information from a moderately long sample of the response signal by retaining only segments satisfying prescribed initial conditions. Different colors denote segments whose initial states lie in different quadrants of the phase space; in this example, only segments originating from the first quadrant are retained. (Bottom) A Moment Aggregation (MA) strategy improves the accuracy of estimated moments by averaging independent realizations of sample moments generated from shifted segmentations.

laxation time of the system [26, 29], ensuring that the influence of the initial conditions has largely decayed before the beginning of the next segment. Direct systematic subdivision would produce segments whose initial values approximately follow the stationary distribution, resulting in nearly stationary moment estimates with very limited dynamical information. Instead, SSS retains only segments satisfying prescribed initial conditions, thereby generating conditional initial distributions that differ from stationarity and preserve transient moment evolution. This procedure enables the extraction of transient stochastic dynamics without repeated experiments or explicit resetting of initial conditions.

The accuracy of moment estimation can be further enhanced through a Moment Aggregation (MA) strategy. Indeed, because moments estimated from finite collections of segments are themselves random variables, their variance decreases with increasing sample size [30, 31]. Building on this observation, the long signal is repeatedly repartitioned by shifting the segmentation starting point, generating multiple independent realizations of sample moments ((b) in Figure 2). Averaging these realizations substantially reduces

estimation standard error and improves robustness under limited data conditions. The resulting error reduction follows directly from the Central Limit Theorem (CLT) [31]. Convergence analysis provided in *SI Appendix, section 3.4 and Appendix B* shows that the estimation error decreases approximately with the number of independent realizations, enabling accurate moment estimation from signals one to two orders of magnitude shorter than those required using SSS alone.

Unlike conventional systematic sliding-window averaging, the proposed aggregation procedure relies on statistical independence between segment realizations; overlapping windows violate this assumption and therefore do not provide equivalent variance reduction [32] (*SI Appendix, Fig. S3(b)*). Together, SSS and MA establish a practical strategy for transient moment estimation from limited response measurements.

Recovery of nonlinear stochastic dynamics

The proposed framework is first examined on a stochastic van der Pol oscillator, a canonical nonlinear system exhibiting self-sustained oscillations and limit-cycle behavior [33] (*SI Appendix, Fig. S4*). Additional validations on stochastic Duffing, Lorenz, and Mathieu systems, representing multistable, chaotic, and multiplicative-noise dynamics, respectively [34, 35, 36], are provided in *SI Appendix, sections 4.1, 4.3, and 4.4*. Owing to its characteristic nonlinear damping and broad physical relevance, the van der Pol oscillator has long served as an effective reduced-order model in fluid dynamics, electrical circuits, and biological systems [37, 38]. In fluid-structure interactions, for example, van der Pol-type oscillators are frequently employed to model vortex-induced vibrations, where turbulent fluctuations perturb the underlying limit-cycle dynamics [39, 40, 41, 42, 43]. Here, we consider a stochastic van der Pol oscillator subjected to additive white-noise forcing

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0.2(1 - z^2) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0.5 \end{bmatrix} \xi_e. \quad (5)$$

Required transient moments are estimated directly from response trajectories. Two datasets are generated: (i) a benchmark dataset obtained from 5×10^5 Monte Carlo realizations initialized from identical initial conditions, $z(0) = \dot{z}(0) = 0$, and (ii) transient moments estimated using the proposed MA strategy from a substantially shorter signal containing 5×10^3 segments, with approximately one quarter retained after selective sampling. The resulting transient moments are shown in Figure 3. They are used as input to the sparse regression procedure.

Despite the substantially reduced data length, the proposed framework accurately recovers the governing stochastic dynamics. As illustrated in Figure 3, the identified system reproduces both the transient moment evolution and the phase-space structure of the exact stochastic oscillator. In particular, the method correctly identifies the cubic nonlinear damping responsible for the limit-cycle behavior together with the additive stochastic forcing term, with the recovered sparse coefficients remaining within 2% of the exact values across all estimation strategies (Figure 1.III, and also *SI Appendix, Table. S3*). These results demonstrate that the framework accurately captures both deterministic and stochastic components of the dynamics from response-only measurements. Additional results presented in the *SI Appendix, section 4.3* demonstrate that the framework scales naturally to higher-dimensional stochastic systems. For a three-dimensional stochastic Lorenz system, the method accurately recovers both drift and diffusion terms. It also successfully separates intrinsic chaotic dynamics from extrinsic stochastic forcing despite strong sensitivity to initial conditions of this chaotic system.

Accurate identification is retained even when moments are estimated from comparatively short response signals using the MA strategy, highlighting the robustness of the framework under limited-data conditions.

Figure 3: Recovery of nonlinear stochastic dynamics from limited response data. Identification results for the stochastic van der Pol oscillator using (Left) transient moments obtained from Monte Carlo simulations and (Right) transient moments estimated using the proposed Moment Aggregation (MA) strategy from a short response signal. Solid lines denote the response moments of the exact system, while dashed lines correspond to the identified model. Insets compare forward simulations of phase-space trajectories of the exact and identified systems, overlaid on the deterministic phase portrait of the van der Pol oscillator.

The method also remains effective for deterministic systems contaminated by substantial measurement noise without requiring prior filtering [13, 1].

The proposed framework differs fundamentally from existing stochastic-discovery approaches based on probability-density evolution or Kramers-Moyal (KM) estimators [44, 45, 46]. Rather than reconstructing the full probability density function or estimating drift and diffusion fields over a discretized state space, the present method operates directly on a finite set of transient statistical moments. This substantially reduces the dimensionality of the identification problem and avoids the numerical differentiation procedures required in FPK-based formulations [15]. In practice, accurate estimation of smooth probability densities typically requires additional kernel-based smoothing or regularization procedures, which may introduce bias and tuning parameters into the identification process [47, 48, 49, 50]. Likewise, KM estimators require accurate estimation of conditional moments throughout the state space, which becomes increasingly demanding as the system dimension grows because sufficiently many samples must be collected within each cell of a high-dimensional state-space discretization. By contrast, the proposed moment-space formulation relies only on a small number of low-order transient moments and therefore remains effective using comparatively short response records. This advantage becomes particularly important for higher-dimensional stochastic systems, where probability-density estimation and state-space discretization rapidly become computationally prohibitive.

Data efficiency and robustness

To assess the robustness of the proposed data-acquisition strategies, the influence of signal length on stochastic system identification is systematically examined. Additional analyses of segment-selection criteria are provided in *SI Appendix, section 4.2.3*. Signal length is characterized by the total number of subdivided segments extracted from the response measurements. Figure 4 compares moment-estimation and the corre-

Figure 4: Data efficiency and robustness of moment-based stochastic discovery. (Left) Relative errors of transient moments estimated using SSS and MA as functions of the number of subdivided segments. (Right) Identification errors quantified by forward-simulation discrepancies between the identified and exact systems.

sponding identification accuracy obtained using either SSS-based sample moments or MA-based moments across varying signal lengths.

The robustness of moment estimation is quantified in Figure 4 (*Left*) through the relative errors of transient moments up to the eighth order, referenced against near-exact Monte Carlo results obtained from 5×10^5 realizations. The MA strategy consistently achieves substantially lower estimation errors than SSS alone over all signal lengths considered. Remarkably, transient moments estimated from approximately 10^2 segments using MA attain accuracy comparable to moments estimated using SSS alone from signals containing approximately 5×10^4 segments. This substantial reduction in data requirements is particularly advantageous for experimental and field applications where acquiring moderately long response signals is difficult or prohibitively expensive.

As expected, identification accuracy closely follows the quality of moment estimation. Figure 4 (*Right*) quantifies the corresponding identification performance through relative errors of forward-simulated displacements compared with the exact stochastic system over the interval $0 \leq t \leq 50$. Consistent with the moment-estimation results, the MA strategy rapidly achieves low simulation errors even when only limited data are available, whereas the SSS-based approach requires substantially longer signals to obtain comparable accuracy. These results demonstrate that improving moment estimation accuracy directly enhances the robustness of stochastic system discovery.

Importantly, the dominant data requirement arises primarily from transient moment estimation rather than from the sparse regression procedure itself. Once reliable moment trajectories are obtained, the identification operates on comparatively short temporal windows. This distinction highlights the central role of moment estimation in enabling accurate output-only discovery of stochastic dynamics from limited response data.

Discussion

We have introduced an output-only framework for discovering nonlinear stochastic differential equations directly from response measurements by operating in moment space rather than state space. By combining

sparse regression with deterministic moment equations, the proposed approach bridges two previously distinct directions in stochastic dynamics: forward statistical analysis based on moment equations and inverse system identification using sparse model discovery. The resulting framework enables parsimonious identification of Langevin-type stochastic systems without requiring synchronized measurements of stochastic excitations.

A central feature of the method is the reformulation of stochastic system identification in terms of transient statistical moments. Because moment equations evolve implicitly with respect to stochastic forcing, the discovery problem can be posed in a low-dimensional deterministic setting while still retaining essential stochastic information. This perspective provides an alternative to existing stochastic discovery approaches based on direct trajectory fitting or high-dimensional probability-density evolution, both of which become challenging when excitation measurements are unavailable or data are limited.

To enable practical implementation under realistic measurement constraints, we further developed SSS and MA strategies for transient moment estimation from a short sample of response signals. The results demonstrate that accurate stochastic discovery depends critically on the quality of transient moment estimation. The MA strategy substantially reduces the data required for reliable inference, enabling comparable identification accuracy from signals that are orders of magnitude shorter than those required using conventional sampling alone. These findings suggest that the primary challenge in output-only stochastic discovery lies in robust statistical estimation rather than in the sparse regression procedure itself.

The proposed framework accurately recovered both deterministic and stochastic components of all systems considered. The method remained robust under strong stochastic forcing and limited-data conditions, while requiring no prior filtering of noisy measurements. In addition to nonlinear oscillators, the framework was successfully applied to a stochastic Lorenz system, demonstrating its applicability to higher-dimensional chaotic dynamics and its ability to quantitatively separate intrinsic chaotic dynamics from extrinsic stochastic forcing. Because the framework operates directly on response statistics, it is particularly attractive for experimental and field applications where repeated measurements or excitation observations are impractical, such as turbulence-driven structural vibrations, fluid-structure interactions, and biological oscillatory systems.

An important limitation arises for systems with multiplicative noise, for which statistically equivalent diffusion representations may produce similar moment dynamics. As discussed in [SI Appendix, section 5](#), this may lead to nonunique stochastic models when only response statistics are available. Incorporating additional physical constraints or prior information may help improve identifiability in such cases.

More broadly, moment equations have long been known effective tools for forward simulation of nonlinear stochastic dynamical systems. Their application in that context, however, is often limited by the closure problem, whereby the evolution of higher-order moments that must be approximated through additional assumptions. By reformulating moment equations as a basis for inverse discovery, the present framework largely circumvents this difficulty: the required higher-order moments are estimated directly from data rather than computed through closure approximations. This perspective establishes a low-dimensional approach for output-only stochastic system identification and opens new opportunities for data-driven modeling of complex stochastic dynamics across science and engineering, including nonlinear oscillatory, multistable, and chaotic systems for which excitation measurements are unavailable or impractical.

Methods

The drift and diffusion functions were represented using polynomial libraries. For the stochastic van der Pol system presented in the main text, polynomial terms up to fifth order were included in the drift library and up to third order in the diffusion library. The resulting moment equations form an infinite hierarchy and were truncated at fourth order, which was found sufficient for accurate stochastic system recovery.

Transient response data were generated using fourth-order Runge-Kutta integration with a time step of 0.05. For the van der Pol example, a long signal was simulated over the interval $0 \leq t \leq 2.5 \times 10^5$, after which the initial transient portion ($0 \leq t \leq 50$) was discarded. The remaining steady-state response was subdivided into short segments of duration 50, yielding approximately 5×10^3 candidate trajectories. Transient moments were then estimated using the proposed MA strategy, conditionally retaining only segments whose initial point lay in the first quadrant of the phase space. Time derivatives of the estimated moments were approximated using a second-order central finite-difference scheme.

Sparse nonlinear regression was performed by minimizing discrepancies between predicted and observed moment derivatives. Because diffusion terms enter the moment equations through quadratic variations of Wiener processes, the optimization problem becomes nonconvex in the diffusion coefficients. Multiple random initializations together with iterative thresholding were therefore employed to promote sparse solutions and improve robustness.

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Supplementary Information

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Abstract. Discovering governing equations of stochastic dynamical systems directly from data remains challenging when stochastic excitations are unobserved and measurements are limited. Existing data-driven approaches either treat stochasticity as measurement noise or rely on high-dimensional probability-density formulations that are computationally difficult to apply in practice. Here, we introduce an output-only framework for discovering nonlinear stochastic differential equations directly from response data by operating in moment space rather than state space. The proposed approach represents drift and diffusion terms as sparse combinations of candidate nonlinear functions and identifies the governing equations through sparse regression on deterministic moment equations derived from stochastic dynamics. Because the formulation evolves implicitly with respect to stochastic forcing, the method enables direct identification of stochastic systems without requiring excitation measurements. To enable robust inference under realistic data limitations, we further develop Selective Segmented Sampling and Moment Aggregation strategies for estimating transient conditional moments from comparatively short stochastic signals. The framework accurately recovers both deterministic and stochastic components of representative nonlinear systems, including stochastic Duffing, van der Pol, Lorenz, and Mathieu systems, demonstrating applicability to multistable, self-excited, chaotic, and multiplicative-noise dynamics even under strong stochastic forcing and limited-data conditions. By combining moment equations with sparse model discovery, the present work establishes a low-dimensional framework for output-only discovery of stochastic dynamics from limited measurements.

Keywords. nonlinear stochastic modeling | stochastic differential equation | moment equations | sparse nonlinear regression | system identification

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and motivations

Many processes of interest across natural sciences, engineering, and socio-economic systems evolve under the combined effects of nonlinear dynamics and random noises. Representative examples include tumor growth driven by stochastic tumor-immune interactions [51], Brownian motion of pollen particles induced by molecular collisions [2], civil engineering structures subjected to random environmental loads such as wind and earthquakes [3], and stock market volatility driven by uncertain factors [4]. In such systems, randomness is not merely a source of measurement noise [1] but a fundamental component shaping the system dynamics. Consequently, their mathematical descriptions are naturally formulated in terms of stochastic differential equations (SDEs) [5].

Traditionally, the structure of these governing equations is derived from first principles, such as conservation of mass, momentum, and thermodynamic properties. However, in many practical situations, the underlying physics may be only partially understood, prohibitively complex, or influenced by unresolved multi-scale interactions [6], rendering first-principles modeling infeasible. In these cases, data-driven modeling offers an attractive alternative by distilling governing equations directly from observed data [7].

Fueled by the rapid growth of high-fidelity datasets and high-performance computing power, along with advanced machine learning algorithms, data-driven system identification that was established in automatic control [8] has gained substantial attention in dynamical systems communities [11]. Despite this progress, most existing identification methods are designed for deterministic systems, while the identification of stochastic systems remains comparatively underexplored. The interplay between strong nonlinearity and intrinsic stochasticity causes identifying SDEs from data significant challenges that go beyond those encountered in deterministic settings [18].

1.2 Existing data-driven methods and their limitations

Over the past several decades, substantial progress has been made in the development of data-driven methods for system identification [10]. Broadly, these methods can be categorized into three classes [7]: fixed-form parametric models informed by expert knowledge, modal decomposition techniques rooted in spectral analysis [52], and flexible numerical models based on symbolic regression or machine learning. Among modal approaches, Koopman operator theory [53] has emerged as a dominant paradigm for analyzing nonlinear dynamical systems by representing their evolution through a linear operator acting on an infinite-dimensional space of observables. As a practical approximation of this framework, Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) [54] provides a low-rank linear representation of large-scale systems in terms of spatial modes oscillating at fixed frequencies with growth or decay rates. In parallel, symbolic regression [55, 7] based on evolutionary computation aims to infer the symbolic structure of governing equations directly from data by searching over a space of candidate expressions. More recently, deep learning techniques [9] have demonstrated remarkable predictive capability in modeling highly complex and nonlinear dynamics, provided that sufficient training data and computational resources are available.

Despite their rapid progress, modern data-driven identification methods face fundamental limitations. In practice, measurement data are often scarce, noisy, and only partially observed, whereas the desired models are expected to remain interpretable, physically meaningful, and capable of extrapolation beyond the training regime [11]. Fixed-form parametric models rely heavily on prior expert knowledge to specify the model structure and may fail when the underlying physics is poorly understood. Linear operator-based methods can struggle to represent strongly nonlinear or state-dependent stochastic dynamics. Symbolic regression approaches, while interpretable, are typically restricted to systems with a small number of interacting variables and incur high computational costs due to the vast search space [55]. Neural network models, depend on the many hidden inner layers, are often uninterpretable, data-hungry, and prone to poor generalization outside the training domain, limiting their reliability in scientific and engineering applications.

These challenges point to the need for parsimonious and interpretable modeling frameworks that balance accuracy and complexity with descriptive capability [56]. Parsimonious models [11] aim to identify the minimal set of mechanisms necessary to explain observed dynamics, thereby reducing the number of free parameters and mitigating overfitting. Such models are inherently more robust to noise, require less data for training, and generalize more reliably by capturing the essential structure of the underlying system rather than spurious correlations in the data.

1.3 SINDy and its extensions to stochastic systems

The advent of the Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics (SINDy) framework [12] marked a turning point in data-driven system identification by providing a parsimonious approach to discovering nonlinear differential equations from data. SINDy exploits the observation that many physical processes are governed

by a small number of dominant mechanisms. By constructing the system dynamics as a sparse linear combination of candidate functions, SINDy formulates model discovery as a sparse regression problem [28] on the time derivatives of the system states. Sparsity-promoting techniques then enable the automatic identification of minimal yet accurate models, yielding interpretable governing equations that balance fidelity and complexity while mitigating overfitting [14]. Since its introduction, SINDy has inspired a broad range of extensions, including identifying partial differential equations [15], incorporating control inputs [14], improving robustness to noisy data through weak formulations and ensembling [13, 1], and probabilistic model discovery via sparse Bayesian learning [57].

Despite these advances, most existing SINDy-based methods are fundamentally designed for deterministic systems [16]. A common strategy for handling stochasticity is to treat random fluctuations as measurement noise contaminating an otherwise deterministic process. While this approximation may be adequate in low-noise regimes, it fails to capture intrinsic stochastic dynamics and cannot recover multiplicative noise structures. Alternative approaches seek to extend SINDy to higher-dimensional representations [19] in order to infer the associated Fokker-Planck equation [17], which governs the evolution of the system’s probability density function. Although theoretically appealing, such methods require high-dimensional probability density data and the numerical estimation of high-order partial derivatives, rendering them impractical for most settings [1]. Consequently, many existing extensions focus primarily on enhancing noise robustness or uncertainty quantification within a deterministic modeling paradigm, rather than identifying stochastic dynamics themselves.

More recent efforts [18, 6] have attempted to adapt SINDy explicitly to stochastic systems by combining sparse regression with the Kramers-Moyal expansion to estimate drift and diffusion terms directly from data. In this class of methods, conditional moments are used to approximate the coefficients of the underlying stochastic differential equation [20], sometimes within a Bayesian framework [5, 16]. However, reliable estimation of Kramers-Moyal coefficients typically requires extensive sampling across many realizations of the stochastic process, leading to high computational cost and severe limitations due to the curse of dimensionality as the system size increases. A separate line of work leverages deep generative models to infer stochastic dynamics in high-dimensional settings, such as HyperSINDy [20], which employs variational encoders [58] to learn distributions over model coefficients. While powerful, these approaches do not target classical SDEs with explicit drift and diffusion terms, but rather random ordinary differential equations [59] whose coefficients are driven by stochastic processes, making them more suitable for parameter uncertainty quantification than for identifying physical stochastic mechanisms.

Taken together, these limitations point to a missing link in data-driven stochastic system identification. On one end of the spectrum are methods that identify SDEs but require full-state observations and synchronized measurements of stochastic excitations; on the other are output-only approaches based on probability density evolution, which demand high-dimensional data and substantial computational resources. What is lacking is an output-only identification framework that operates directly in a low-dimensional deterministic equation space but implicitly accounts for stochastic dynamics through response data alone.

1.4 Prospect of using moment equations

Since early developments, stochastic dynamics have been described either at the microscopic level through stochastic differential equations, as formalized by Itô [25], or at the macroscopic level through partial differential equations, as introduced by Fokker and Planck [26], tracking the ensemble evolution of probability distributions in a high-dimensional continuous space. Between these two extremes, however, there exists a natural intermediate description based on statistical moments. Moments provide low-dimensional characterization but encapsulate essential information about probability distributions without requiring their full

resolution. This intermediate representation is formalized through moment equations, which constitute a hierarchy of deterministic ordinary differential equations governing the time evolution of response moments of any order. Moment equations can be derived either by taking expectations of Itô’s formula applied directly to the SDEs [21] or by applying integral transforms, such as the Mellin transform [27], to the corresponding Fokker-Planck equation. Since the seminal work of Grigoriu [60], moment equations have been shown to be effective in analyzing non-Gaussian processes [61] and nonlinear systems subjected to parametric and external noise [24]. More recent studies [22, 23] have demonstrated their computational efficiency and accuracy for nonstationary stochastic vibration analysis, including systems with time-varying parameters.

From a theoretical standpoint, moment equations can be interpreted as a projection of the infinite-dimensional partial differential equation onto a discrete, low-dimensional ordinary differential equation space indexed by integer moment orders. This dimensional reduction makes moment equations particularly attractive for data-driven modeling, where data availability and noise robustness are critical constraints. While classical SINDy formulations rely on minimizing discrepancies in time derivatives of state trajectories and therefore require access to excitation data, moment equations evolve implicitly on excitations. By formulating identification problems in terms of the time derivatives of statistical moments, one can infer the governing drift and diffusion structures of stochastic systems using response data alone. This moment-equation-based perspective thus enables an output-only system identification framework for the discovery of hidden stochastic dynamics without direct observation of the excitations.

1.5 Outline

This study presents a novel output-only stochastic system discovery framework for inferring nonlinear stochastic differential equations based on moment-equation techniques. To enable practical implementation under realistic data limitations, a Selective Segmented Sampling (SSS) data-acquisition strategy together with a Moment Aggregation (MA) strategy is developed to estimate high-fidelity transient statistical moments from comparatively short time-series records, which are subsequently used to inform the identification. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the derivation of moment equations for a general class of nonlinear stochastic oscillators subjected to both additive and multiplicative noise, providing the theoretical foundation for the proposed approach. Section 3 introduces the stochastic system identification framework in detail: nonlinear Langevin-type SDEs are represented as sparse linear combinations of candidate functions; moment equations are derived from these sparsely parameterized representations; loss functions are constructed based on discrepancies between predicted and observed time derivatives of the moments; and a two-phase sparse nonlinear regression algorithm is developed to identify the sparse coefficients. Section 4 demonstrates the performance of the proposed method through four representative examples: single-well and double-well Duffing oscillators driven by additive white noise, a van der Pol oscillator under external stochastic excitation, a stochastic Lorenz system exhibiting chaotic dynamics, and a stochastic Mathieu equation with parametric noise. In addition, the robustness of the proposed moment estimation strategies and the uniqueness of the identification models are discussed.

2 Moment equations for nonlinear stochastic oscillators

The dynamics of nonlinear systems under stochastic perturbations are often studied from a statistical perspective, typically through probability density functions (PDFs) or statistical moments. This section formulates the governing equations for the time evolution of the moments for a given class of nonlinear stochastic systems, thereby providing an essential basis for the stochastic system identification method introduced in

Section 3.

2.1 Equation of motion

This study is concerned with 2nd order time-invariant dynamical systems with typical nonlinearities and subjected to stochastic excitations induced by white noise

$$\mathbf{M}_0\ddot{\mathbf{z}} + [\mathbf{C}_0 + \mathbf{C}_1(\mathbf{z}, \dot{\mathbf{z}}) + \mathbf{C}_2(\mathbf{z}, \dot{\mathbf{z}})\xi_d]\dot{\mathbf{z}} + [\mathbf{K}_0 + \mathbf{K}_1(\mathbf{z}) + \mathbf{K}_2(\mathbf{z})\xi_s]\mathbf{z} = \sigma_e\xi_e, \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{M}_0 , \mathbf{C}_0 and \mathbf{K}_0 are the linear mass, damping and stiffness matrices, respectively. The matrix \mathbf{C}_1 denotes the nonlinear damping coefficient, as in the van der Pol oscillator [33], and the matrix \mathbf{K}_1 denotes the nonlinear stiffness coefficient, as in the Duffing oscillator [34]. The terms $\mathbf{C}_2\xi_d$ and $\mathbf{K}_2\xi_s$ describe the damping- and stiffness-related parametric noise excitations (also known as multiplicative noises), commonly appearing in stochastic Mathieu-type systems [36]. The term $\sigma_e\xi_e$ is the external noise excitation (or additive noise). The stochastic processes ξ_d , ξ_s and ξ_e are independent standard Gaussian white noises, and \mathbf{z} is the vector of generalized coordinates.

The stochastic nonlinear dynamical equation Eq. (6) is transformed into the corresponding state-space form

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{z} \\ \dot{\mathbf{z}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{1} \\ -\mathbf{M}_0^{-1}(\mathbf{K}_0 + \mathbf{K}_1) & -\mathbf{M}_0^{-1}(\mathbf{C}_0 + \mathbf{C}_1) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{z} \\ \dot{\mathbf{z}} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{M}_0^{-1}\sigma_e & -\mathbf{M}_0^{-1}\mathbf{K}_2 & -\mathbf{M}_0^{-1}\mathbf{C}_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \xi_e \\ \xi_s \\ \xi_d \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

2.2 Stochastic differential equations

Eq. (7) can be recognized as a nonlinear Langevin-type stochastic differential equation (SDE) of the form

$$d\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})dt + \sigma(\mathbf{x})d\mathbf{w}, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(t)$ is the vector of system states, e.g., $\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{z} \ \dot{\mathbf{z}}]^T$. In the *drift* term, the nonlinear function $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$ characterises the deterministic part of the dynamics, while the *diffusion* term $\sigma(\mathbf{x})d\mathbf{w}$ accounts for the stochastic excitations. Here, $\mathbf{w}(t)$ denotes a vector of mutually independent Wiener processes, e.g., $d\mathbf{w}/dt = [\xi_e \ \xi_s \ \xi_d]^T$. The particular case of constant σ corresponds to the additive noise only, whereas the state-dependent case $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ can emulate multiplicative noise. Note that the functions $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$ and $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ are assumed not to explicitly depend on time.

Although Eq. (8) (and the subsequent moment equations) is derived under the assumption of white noise excitation, nonlinear oscillators driven by coloured noise ξ_e can be readily accommodated by approximating the coloured noise by a filtered white noise. A common choice is the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) process $\bar{\xi}_e$, which satisfies the stochastic differential equation

$$d\bar{\xi}_e = -\theta_e\bar{\xi}_e dt + \sigma_e d\mathbf{w}, \quad (9)$$

where θ_e, σ_e are positive coefficients, and \mathbf{w} is a standard Wiener process. By appending Eq. (9) to Eq. (8), the augmented states composed of \mathbf{x} and $\bar{\xi}_e$ can be expressed in the same Langevin form, thus enabling unified treatment of both white- and coloured-noise excitations within the same framework.

Given the SDE in Eq. (8), the corresponding FPK equation governing the time evolution of the joint probability density function $p(\mathbf{x}, t)$ of the system states is derived as

$$\frac{\partial p(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} = - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} [f_i(\mathbf{x}) p(\mathbf{x}, t)] + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} [D_{ij}(\mathbf{x}) p(\mathbf{x}, t)], \quad (10)$$

where x_i denotes the i -th component of \mathbf{x} , $f_i(\mathbf{x})$ is the i -th component of $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$, and $D_{ij}(\mathbf{x})$ is the (i, j) -th component of the diffusion matrix $\boldsymbol{\sigma}\boldsymbol{\sigma}^T$. The upper limit n denotes the dimension of the system.

The joint PDF $p(\mathbf{x}, t)$ provides a complete statistical description of the stochastic response in a continuous, high-dimensional state space. However, in many practical settings, working directly with the full probability density is computationally prohibitive. Instead, one may consider low-dimensional statistics in the form of joint moments, defined over a discrete space of integer orders as

$$m(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x_1^{a_1} x_2^{a_2} \dots x_n^{a_n} p(\mathbf{x}, t) d\mathbf{x}, \quad (11)$$

where a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n are non-negative integers, and $m(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ denotes the joint moment of the state variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n . The total order of the moment is defined as $\sum_{i=1}^n a_i$.

2.3 Unclosed moment equations

Once the SDE in Eq. (8) is specified, the corresponding hierarchy of moment equations can be derived either by applying the defined \mathcal{M} -transform to the associated FPK equation in Eq. (10) [62] or by taking the expectation of Itô's formula [23]. For any prescribed truncation order s , this procedure yields a finite set of coupled deterministic equations in the general form

$$\dot{\mathbf{m}}_L = \mathbf{P}_1 \mathbf{m}_L + \mathbf{P}_2 \mathbf{m}_H + \mathbf{Q}, \quad (12)$$

where the vector \mathbf{m}_L collects all moments $m(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ whose total order $\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \leq s$, while \mathbf{m}_H collects all higher-order moments beyond this cut-off. The coefficient matrices \mathbf{P}_1 , \mathbf{P}_2 , and \mathbf{Q} are known and determined by the system and excitation parameters. Note that $\mathbf{P}_2 \mathbf{m}_H$ results from the nonlinear terms in Eq. (6).

In contrast with the partial differential equation form in Eq. (10), the resulting moment equations in Eq. (12) constitute a low-dimensional system of first-order ordinary differential equations governing the time evolution of statistical moments of the system response. For brevity, the detailed derivations are not repeated here. The reader is referred to the original work [60] and the authors' previous publications [22, 23] for a comprehensive exposition of the theoretical framework and derivation procedures.

A fundamental challenge associated with the moment-equation framework is the so-called closure problem. For linear systems, moments of increasing total order s can be computed sequentially from lower-order moments ($\sum_{i=1}^n a_i < s$), which are already known from the previous steps of computation. These lower-order moments either vanish (for any negative exponent) or take the known value of unity (for $a_1 = \dots = a_n = 0$), allowing the equations to be closed and solved in a recursive manner. However, in the presence of nonlinearities and parametric stochasticities, higher-order moments appear in Eq. (12) and render the equations unclosed, that is, the evolution of moments of order s depends on moments of higher orders ($\sum_{i=1}^n a_i > s$) that have not yet been determined. To illustrate unclosed moment equations, consider the nonlinear system of a unimodal Duffing oscillator under additive white noise

$$d \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ -x_1 - \epsilon x_1^3 \end{bmatrix} dt + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \sigma \end{bmatrix} dw, \quad (13)$$

where ϵ is the nonlinearity parameter, and σ denotes the noise intensity. The corresponding truncated moment equations for moments up to second order are derived as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} m(1,0) \\ m(0,1) \\ m(2,0) \\ m(1,1) \\ m(0,2) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} m(1,0) \\ m(0,1) \\ m(2,0) \\ m(1,1) \\ m(0,2) \end{bmatrix} - \epsilon \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} m(3,0) \\ m(4,0) \\ m(3,1) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \sigma^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

It is evident that the time derivatives of the first- and second-order moments depend on the third- and fourth-order moments, which cannot be directly computed from these truncated moment equations. To make the problem solvable, additional closure techniques are typically introduced, such as the cumulant-neglect closure method [24] which assumes that the cumulants above a certain order are negligible due to their relatively small magnitudes. Nevertheless, this assumption is not universally valid across nonlinear systems: as reported by Wojtkiewicz, for instance, the method fails to predict the response of a bimodal Duffing oscillator under additive noise, even when the closure order is increased. In contrast, when $\epsilon = 0$, the system reduces to a linear undamped oscillator and the moment equations are closed, as higher-order moments do not enter the evolution of lower-order ones, allowing the equations to be solved sequentially.

Although such closure issues are inevitable when directly solving nonlinear stochastic vibrations, the proposed system identification method, as detailed later, circumvents this difficulty through its designed procedure. This constitutes one of the key advantages of the approach.

3 Proposed stochastic sparse identification method

This section describes a new sparse identification framework for nonlinear stochastic dynamics based on moment equations, complemented by a data-acquisition scheme that can readily obtain the required statistical data either from simulations or limited experimental measurements. Importantly, the proposed identification method is output-only, meaning that only the response signals (i.e., system states) need to be measured. This feature makes the approach particularly suitable for practical scenarios in which external forcing is unobservable. As the proposed framework is partially inspired by SINDy, we first revisit its key features before introducing the present approach.

3.1 Sparse representation of drift and diffusion functions

Instead of directly fitting a prescribed nonlinear function to the time-series data, i.e., the measurement, SINDy represents the deterministic nonlinear governing equations $dx = f(x)dt$ as a linear combination of candidate functions by sparse coefficients, so that sparse linear regression techniques can be used to optimise the coefficient matrix as a sparse one. In the optimisation, SINDy directs its focus towards the time derivatives of states, i.e., LHS of the governing equation, which can be obtained, without solving equations, either through substituting the measurement at each time instant into the RHS, as the prediction $f(\hat{x})$, or from the finite time difference of the measurement, as the observation $\hat{\dot{x}}$, so that possible discrepancies $\|\hat{\dot{x}} - f(\hat{x})\|$ are present and thus to be minimized, where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the matrix norm.

The elegance of SINDy lies in two key aspects. First, by defining the observation (or prediction) as a time-evolution process, the discrepancies are minimized not only in the steady state but also during the transient phase, thereby enabling an effective identification of the system dynamics. Second, the observation (or prediction) must be a deterministic quantity, so that the discrepancies can be minimized on a consistent

basis. Note that this is not the case for stochastic systems, as the random time derivatives cannot be reliably predicted due to a lack of excitation data or to difficulties in synchronizing measurements.

To extend the method to stochastic systems while preserving the above methodological philosophies, this study shifts the focus to statistical moments, because (a) the moments are essentially deterministic; (b) their time derivatives can be easily predicted through moment equations (as reported in Eq. (12)), thereby capturing the transient effect; and remarkably (c) they provide a low-dimensional, discrete set of observation, as opposed to probability density functions, ensuring high computational efficiency and practical feasibility.

In this study, we focus on discovering stochastic dynamical systems that can be represented by a nonlinear Langevin-type SDE as reported in Eq. (8). The problem of concern is to identify the nonlinear functions of the drift term $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$ and diffusion coefficients $\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x})$. The symbolic drift and diffusion functions are represented by linear combinations of candidate nonlinear functions with a sparse matrix of coefficients, such that

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \Xi_{\mathbf{f}} \Theta_{\mathbf{f}}(\mathbf{x}), \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}) = \Xi_{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \Theta_{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}(\mathbf{x}), \quad (15)$$

where the function libraries $\Theta_{\mathbf{f}}(\mathbf{x})$, $\Theta_{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}(\mathbf{x})$ are column vectors that consist of symbolic candidate functions, e.g., for a two-state SDE, they may be constructed as

$$\Theta_g(\mathbf{x}) = [1 \quad x_1 \quad x_2 \quad x_1^2 \quad x_1 x_2 \quad x_2^2 \quad \cdots]^T, \quad (16)$$

where the subscript $g \in \{\mathbf{f}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}\}$. The matrices $\Xi_{\mathbf{f}}$, $\Xi_{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ consist of sparse row vectors of coefficients, with each row ξ_k determining which candidate functions are activated for the corresponding drift component $\mathbf{f}_k(\mathbf{x})$ and the diffusion component $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_k(\mathbf{x})$, as illustrated in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Schematic overview of the proposed sparse identification framework for nonlinear stochastic dynamics based on moment equations, illustrated for the van der Pol oscillator subjected to additive white noise. **I.** A moderately long time series of stochastic responses, including the state variables x and \dot{x} , is acquired from measurements of the nonlinear stochastic system. **II.** Statistical moments up to a prescribed truncation order are estimated from the measured data using the proposed Selective Segmented Sampling (SSS) approach. **III.** The drift and diffusion functions are expressed as linear combinations of candidate nonlinear basis functions with sparse coefficient matrices. **IV.** Deterministic moment equations are derived from the sparsely parameterized stochastic differential equations. **V.** By incorporating the estimated moment data and applying sparse nonlinear regression, the coefficient matrices are identified through minimization of the discrepancy between predicted and observed time derivatives of the moments.

Using these sparse representations, the overall SDE becomes

$$d\mathbf{x} = \Xi_f \Theta_f(\mathbf{x})dt + \Xi_\sigma \Theta_\sigma(\mathbf{x})d\mathbf{w}. \quad (17)$$

The task now reduces to the identification of two sparse matrices Ξ_f and Ξ_σ , which can be formulated as a standard sparse regression problem.

3.2 Loss function on moment derivatives

The proposed approach seeks to optimize the coefficient matrices by minimizing the discrepancies between the predicted and observed time derivatives of the moments. Given the explicit SDE form of Eq. (17), the moment equations can be constructed, following the procedure described in Section 2, as a set of deterministic first-order ordinary differential equations (ODEs)

$$\dot{\mathbf{m}}_L(t) = \mathbf{P}_1(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma) \mathbf{m}_L(t) + \mathbf{P}_2(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma) \mathbf{m}_H(t) + \mathbf{Q}(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma), \quad (18)$$

where now the coefficient functions \mathbf{P}_1 , \mathbf{P}_2 , and \mathbf{Q} are linear in Ξ_f but quadratic in Ξ_σ . The quadratic terms arise from the quadratic variations of Wiener processes, and result in a nonlinear regression in Ξ_σ . The uniqueness of the identification due to these terms will be discussed in Section 5.

As indicated in Section 2, Eq. (18) seems not closed, because the lower-order moment equations depend on the unsolved higher-order moments. Unlike forward simulations, closure of Eq. (18) is not required in the identification (inverse) problem. Since both low-order and high-order moments are available as known statistical data, the time derivatives on the LHS can be predicted algebraically by substituting the time-series data of moments into the RHS, rather than solving ODEs. All required moments can be estimated from time-history samples of the system states. This feature eliminates the need for complex closure techniques, which is often a major limitation in forward simulations. A practical data-acquisition scheme for estimating the required moments from simulations or experiments is introduced in Section 3.4.

As the moments evolve over time, which reflects the system's dynamical behaviour, they are estimated at discrete time instants and assembled in a large data matrix, e.g.,

$$\mathbf{M}_L = [\mathbf{m}_L(t_1) \quad \mathbf{m}_L(t_2) \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{m}_L(t_m)] = \begin{bmatrix} m_{L,1}(t_1) & m_{L,1}(t_2) & \cdots & m_{L,1}(t_m) \\ m_{L,2}(t_1) & m_{L,2}(t_2) & \cdots & m_{L,2}(t_m) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ m_{L,n}(t_1) & m_{L,n}(t_2) & \cdots & m_{L,n}(t_m) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

By substituting the moment data at each time instant, one obtains a matrix collecting the predicted time derivatives of the moments over all time instants

$$\hat{\mathbf{M}}_L = [\hat{\mathbf{m}}_L(t_1) \quad \hat{\mathbf{m}}_L(t_2) \quad \cdots \quad \hat{\mathbf{m}}_L(t_m)] = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{m}_{L,1}(t_1) & \hat{m}_{L,1}(t_2) & \cdots & \hat{m}_{L,1}(t_m) \\ \hat{m}_{L,2}(t_1) & \hat{m}_{L,2}(t_2) & \cdots & \hat{m}_{L,2}(t_m) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \hat{m}_{L,n}(t_1) & \hat{m}_{L,n}(t_2) & \cdots & \hat{m}_{L,n}(t_m) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

The predicted matrix can be determined in a collective form through Eq. (18)

$$\hat{\mathbf{M}}_L = \mathbf{P}_1(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma)\mathbf{M}_L + \mathbf{P}_2(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma)\mathbf{M}_H + \mathbf{Q}(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma)\mathbf{I}_m, \quad (21)$$

where \mathbf{I}_m is an m -dimension row vector of 1.

The time derivatives of the moments can also be numerically approximated from the data \mathbf{M}_L through finite difference scheme, yielding the observation matrix $\dot{\mathbf{M}}_L$. The sparse coefficient matrices Ξ_f^{opt} and Ξ_σ^{opt} will be identified by minimizing the discrepancies between predicted and observed time derivatives of the moments, leading to the following optimisation problem

$$(\Xi_f^{\text{opt}}, \Xi_\sigma^{\text{opt}}) = \arg \min_{\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma} L(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma), \quad (22)$$

in which the loss function $L(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma)$ is defined as

$$L(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma) = \|\mathbf{P}_1(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma)\mathbf{M}_L + \mathbf{P}_2(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma)\mathbf{M}_H + \mathbf{Q}(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma)\mathbf{I}_m - \dot{\mathbf{M}}_L\|_F^2, \quad (23)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the Frobenius norm.

3.3 Two-phase sparse nonlinear regression

Unlike classical sparse linear regression models, in which \mathbf{P}_1 , \mathbf{P}_2 and \mathbf{Q} depend linearly on the coefficients to be identified, allowing the use of well-established sparse regression algorithms such as LASSO or sequential thresholded least-squares, the quadratic dependence of these matrices on Ξ_σ renders the loss

function (23) nonconvex, thereby preventing such algorithms from reliably reaching the global minimum. As a nonconvex global optimisation problem, it is generally impossible to guarantee that the exact global minimum has been reached. A practical remedy is to perform multiple local optimisations from different random initializations and examine whether the best (lowest) objective value obtained is consistent across runs. If the identified coefficient matrices remain sparse and yield the lowest achievable loss, the solution can be regarded as an approximate global optimum.

Thus, this study introduces a two-phase sparse nonlinear regression algorithm to seek a sparse solution at which the lowest value of the loss function occurs. In the first phase, the algorithm performs multiple local minimizations of an L1-regularized loss function, defined below, starting from random initializations

$$J(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma) = L(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma) + \lambda_f \|\Xi_f\|_1 + \lambda_\sigma \|\Xi_\sigma\|_1, \quad (24)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_1$ denotes the elementwise L1-norm of a matrix, i.e., the sum of the absolute values of all entries. The coefficients λ_f and λ_σ are regularization parameters. Similar to the LASSO regression, the L1 penalty terms naturally drive negligible coefficients to zero, enabling function selection and sparsity in the identified model.

The optimization tolerance in the first phase can be set to a moderate level, as the objective is to rapidly locate the regions most likely containing the global optimum. The best solution found in this stage serves as the initialization for the second phase. In the second phase, a sequential thresholded minimization is applied iteratively to the unregularized loss function $L(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma)$. After each iteration, coefficients with magnitudes below a prescribed cut-off value are set to zero, and their indices are recorded in a Boolean mask indicating inactive terms. In the subsequent iteration, the optimization is restarted from the current thresholded coefficients, during which additional small-magnitude coefficients may be further eliminated. Newly deactivated terms are added to the existing mask, while previously removed ones remain fixed at zero. This iterative process continues until the set of non-zero coefficients converges.

The proposed two-phase algorithm combines the advantages of both the LASSO and the sequential thresholded least-squares algorithms used in SINDy. The coefficient-reduction feature of L1 regularization enables the automatic correction of sparsity patterns and provides a robust initialization, whereas the subsequent thresholded optimization enforces strict and irreversible sparsity. This design prevents premature elimination of relevant terms and guides the optimization toward an accurate convergence. The resulting algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1, which is implemented in Python.

Algorithm 1: Two-phase sparse nonlinear regression algorithm for Eq. (22)

Input: Statistical data $\mathbf{M}_L, \mathbf{M}_H$, observation $\dot{\mathbf{M}}_L$, regularization parameters $\lambda_f, \lambda_\sigma$, maximum numbers of iterations $S_1, S_2 > 0$, standard deviation of initial Gaussian distribution $\sigma > 0$, tolerance $\text{tol} > 0$, threshold $\alpha > 0$

Phase 1: L1-regularized optimisation

Initialization: Construct coefficient functions $\mathbf{P}_1, \mathbf{P}_2, \mathbf{Q}$, set the iteration counter $i \leftarrow 0$

Repeat

Random initialization: $\Xi_{f0}, \Xi_{\sigma0} \leftarrow N(0, \sigma)$

Perform minimization: $(\Xi_{f1}^{(i)}, \Xi_{\sigma1}^{(i)}) = \arg \min_{\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma} J(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma)$ initialized at $(\Xi_{f0}, \Xi_{\sigma0})$

Update: $i \leftarrow i + 1$

Until $i = S_1$;

Phase 2: Sequential thresholded optimization

Initialization: $\Xi_{f2}^{(0)}, \Xi_{\sigma2}^{(0)} \leftarrow \text{global optimum}\{\Xi_{f1}^{(i)}, \Xi_{\sigma1}^{(i)} : 0 \leq i < S_1\}$,

$\text{switch}_f, \text{switch}_\sigma \leftarrow \text{bool}(\text{abs}(\Xi_{f2}^{(0)}), \text{abs}(\Xi_{\sigma2}^{(0)}) < \alpha)$, set the iteration counter $i \leftarrow 0$

Repeat

Perform minimization: $(\Xi_{f2}^{(i+1)}, \Xi_{\sigma2}^{(i+1)}) = \arg \min_{\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma} L(\Xi_f, \Xi_\sigma)$ initialized at $(\Xi_{f2}^{(i)}, \Xi_{\sigma2}^{(i)})$

Record small value indices: $\text{switch}_f^t, \text{switch}_\sigma^t \leftarrow \text{bool}(\text{abs}(\Xi_{f2}^{(i+1)}), \text{abs}(\Xi_{\sigma2}^{(i+1)}) < \alpha)$

Update switches: $\text{switch}_f += \text{switch}_f^t, \text{switch}_\sigma += \text{switch}_\sigma^t$

Threshold coefficients: $\Xi_{f2}^{(i+1)}[\text{switch}_f] = 0, \Xi_{\sigma2}^{(i+1)}[\text{switch}_\sigma] = 0$

Update: $i \leftarrow i + 1$

Until $L(\Xi_{f2}^{(i)}, \Xi_{\sigma2}^{(i)}) < \text{tol}$ or $i = S_2$;

Output: Sparse coefficient matrices $\Xi_f^{\text{opt}}, \Xi_\sigma^{\text{opt}} \leftarrow \Xi_{f2}^{(i)}, \Xi_{\sigma2}^{(i)}$

3.4 Data acquisition by selective segmented sampling

As a prerequisite to the proposed identification algorithm, high-quality input data are required in the form of time-varying statistical moments. However, acquiring such data is far more challenging than measuring state trajectories, since reliable statistical estimation demands a sufficiently large number of samples. Moreover, to adequately capture the system dynamics, the measurement in the transient phase is preferably comparable to that of the steady state. In practice, however, obtaining such rich samples experimentally is hardly feasible, because (a) conducting numerous long-run tests is prohibitively expensive, and (b) resetting the system to identical initial conditions (e.g., zero initial states) after each run is both technically demanding and time-consuming. The situation is even more restrictive in field measurements, where only a single or a few long-term records are typically available.

To enhance the practical applicability of the proposed framework, this section introduces a data-acquisition strategy (see Fig. 6) that can reliably estimate the required moment data from a single, moderately long, measured signal. The basic idea is to subdivide the signal into multiple segments of equal length, chosen longer than the *memory time* of the system. This memory time can be estimated as the duration of the transient response after impulsive input. The statistical moments are then evaluated over these segments. However, because the initial values of these segments essentially correspond to systematic subsampling of a long-term signal, whose values in fact follow quickly a stationary probability distribution, the resulting moments tend to remain constant, thereby failing to capture the system's transient behavior.

Figure 6: Selective Segmented Sampling data-acquisition scheme.

Instead of the systematic subsampling, one may in principle consider selecting only those segments that start from an identical initial point (or a narrowly defined initial zone), which corresponds to a delta-function initial distribution. Because such an initial distribution differs from the stationary one, the resulting moments would naturally exhibit a transient phase before converging to steady state. However, such a manner would require an excessively long time series to ensure a sufficient number of matching segments, which is generally impractical. To recover transient moment evolution without enforcing tight equality of initial values, a more flexible segment-selection strategy is therefore introduced. Specifically, a mild constraint is imposed on the segment selection. For instance, selecting only segments whose initial values are positive yields a conditional initial distribution as the normalized partial PDF in the first quadrant. This selection retains approximately one quarter of the total segments while preserving the transient evolution of the moments. This data-acquisition method is referred to as Selective Segmented Sampling (SSS). As will be demonstrated later, the SSS approach effectively complements the proposed stochastic identification framework, allowing reliable system recovery even under limited measurement conditions.

Beyond ensuring transient information, the accuracy of the moments estimated via SSS can be further improved by invoking the central limit theorem (CLT). In essence, the moments estimated from a finite sample of segments are themselves random variables, hereafter referred to as sample moments, whose randomness arises from the particular realization of signal segmentation. According to the classical CLT, as the number of selected segments increases, these sample moments converge to a normal distribution centered at the true moment value (e.g., $\mathbb{E}[X^a]$), with a variance (e.g., $(\mathbb{E}[X^{2a}] - (\mathbb{E}[X^a])^2)/n$) that decreases with increasing sample size n (see A for a detailed derivation).

Building on this observation, an alternative segmentation manner is considered. Instead of performing SSS only once, the long time series can be subdivided repeatedly by shifting the starting point of segmentation along the signal, thereby generating multiple collections of short segments (see Fig. 7). Applying the SSS procedure to each realization yields an ensemble of sample moments of size k . By virtue of the Lyapunov CLT, the arithmetic mean of these sample moments converges almost surely to the true moment,

with a variance, e.g.,

$$(\mathbb{E}[X^{2a}] - (\mathbb{E}[X^a])^2) \frac{1}{k^2} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{1}{n_i}. \quad (25)$$

Convergence analysis (see B) demonstrates that this Moment Aggregation (MA) procedure can reduce the estimation variance by several orders of magnitude, proportional to the number of realizations k , compared to using a single realization. In addition to the simple arithmetic averaging, weighted averaging of sample moments, i.e.,

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \sqrt{n_i} \langle X^a \rangle_{n_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^k \sqrt{n_i}} \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N} \left(\mathbb{E}[X^a], (\mathbb{E}[X^{2a}] - (\mathbb{E}[X^a])^2) \frac{k}{(\sum_{i=1}^k \sqrt{n_i})^2} \right), \quad (26)$$

can be employed to further improve estimation accuracy, as discussed in the B.

Figure 7: Enhanced moment estimation by aggregating sample moments by invoking the central limit theorem (top). Biased estimation of sample moments over overlapping segments (bottom).

From a practical perspective, one may be concerned that acquiring a moderately long time signal required by SSS may itself be challenging in experiments or simulations. The Moment Aggregation (MA) strategy alleviates this limitation: by averaging multiple realizations of sample moments, comparable accuracy can be achieved using substantially shorter datasets, for instance, signals that are one to two orders of magnitude shorter, depending on the number of realizations. It is important to distinguish this averaging approach from estimating moments using overlapping segments obtained by sliding a short window along the time signal (see Fig. 7). Reliable convergence under the CLT requires that the segments being averaged have to be mutually independent. Clearly, overlapping segments do not satisfy this requirement, leading to biased variance reduction.

4 Results

The proposed stochastic system identification framework is demonstrated on four representative examples of increasing complexity. The first example considers the classical Duffing oscillator driven by additive white noise, including both single-well and double-well potential cases, to assess the method's ability to capture nonlinear stiffness and multi-stable dynamics. The second example examines the van der Pol oscillator under external white-noise excitation, a canonical nonlinear system exhibiting self-sustained oscillations and limit-cycle behavior. For this case, where moment equations cannot be closed using conventional cumulant-neglect techniques, the proposed Selective Segmented Sampling and Moment Aggregation strategies are employed to estimate transient moments from a long response sample. The third example considers a stochastic Lorenz system subjected to additive white noise, demonstrating the applicability of the proposed framework to higher-dimensional chaotic dynamics. Finally, the method is applied to a stochastic Mathieu equation with parametric excitation, illustrating the non-uniqueness of identified models arising from state-dependent noise, a phenomenon discussed further in Section 5. The phase portraits of the deterministic Duffing and van der Pol oscillators and the stability region of the stochastic Mathieu equation are illustrated in Fig. 8. The deterministic and stochastic Lorenz attractors are shown later in Section 4.3.

Figure 8: Phase portraits of the single-well Duffing oscillator featuring a stable focus (top left), the double-well Duffing oscillator featuring two stable foci (top right), and the van der Pol oscillator featuring a limit cycle (bottom left); and the stability region on the plane of parameters c_0, k_0, σ_s of a stochastic Mathieu equation (bottom right).

4.1 Duffing oscillator forced by additive white noise

As a first example, the classical Duffing oscillator with cubic nonlinearity and subjected to strong additive white noise is considered [34], examined in both monostable, as in Eq. (27), and bistable, as in Eq. (28), configurations

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 - 0.1z^2 & -0.4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \xi_e, \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 - 0.1z^2 & -0.4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \xi_e. \quad (28)$$

Since the moment equations of the unimodal Duffing system can be effectively closed using cumulant-neglect closure, the required moment data are obtained by solving the corresponding moment equations closed at an order of 8, up to which all moments are evaluated. The time series of moments are collected over the interval $0 \leq t \leq 50$ with a time step of 0.1. This simulation window sufficiently covers the transient phase of the response, which can be estimated around 10, as shown in Fig. 9. The resulting mean squared displacements and velocities are shown in Fig. 9. The time derivatives of the moments are directly obtained from the governing moment equations by substituting the computed moment data into the RHS.

Figure 9: Comparison of time-series moments (top) and phase portraits (bottom) for the exact stochastic Duffing systems with single-well potential (left) and double-well potential (right) and the identified systems.

The function library for the drift term includes polynomial combinations of z and \dot{z} up to the fifth degree, while that for the diffusion term is up to the third degree

$$\Theta_{\mathbf{f}}(\mathbf{x}) = [1 \quad z \quad \dot{z} \quad z^2 \quad z\dot{z} \quad \dot{z}^2 \quad \dots \quad \dot{z}^5]^T, \quad (29)$$

$$\Theta_{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}) = [1 \quad z \quad \dot{z} \quad z^2 \quad z\dot{z} \quad \dot{z}^2 \quad \dots \quad \dot{z}^3]^T. \quad (30)$$

It is important to note that, in general, reliable estimation of statistical moments from raw response data requires sufficiently long time series to ensure statistical convergence. In the present example, however, the moment data are obtained by solving the closed moment equations, thereby bypassing the need for long Monte Carlo simulations. This allows the identification procedure to operate on relatively short time windows, highlighting that the data requirement primarily arises from moment estimation rather than the sparse regression step itself.

During the system identification process, because the moment equations Eq. (18) form an infinite hierarchy of equations, they are truncated at the fourth order, which is found sufficient to achieve accurate identification results. For the bistable Duffing system, the cumulant-neglect closure fails to accurately predict response moments. The moment data are therefore estimated from Monte Carlo simulations by integrating Eq. (28) using the Runge-Kutta method, The time derivatives are then approximated from the estimated moments using a second-order central finite difference scheme. The collected data are presented in Fig. 9. A systematic discussion on the selection of moment estimation strategies and signal length is provided in Section 4.2.

The proposed stochastic system identification algorithm successfully recovers the exact terms of the SDEs in each case. The predictions of the identified models are illustrated in Fig. 9, where sample trajectories are generated from identical initial conditions and subjected to the same stochastic excitations for direct comparison. The identified sparse coefficients are summarized in Table 1 and Table 2, with discrepancies consistently within 3.3% of the true values, demonstrating the excellent accuracy of the proposed method.

Table 1: Identified sparse coefficients of drift and diffusion functions for stochastic single-well Duffing system (functions with thresholded coefficients are omitted here for brevity).

Function library	1	z	\dot{z}	z^3
Drift (z)	0	0	1	0
Drift (\dot{z})	0	-1	-0.4	-0.1
Diffusion (z)	0	0	0	0
Diffusion (\dot{z})	1	0	0	0

Table 2: Identified sparse coefficients of drift and diffusion functions for stochastic double-well Duffing system (functions with thresholded coefficients are omitted here for brevity).

Function library	1	z	\dot{z}	z^3
Drift (z)	0	0	1.004	0
Drift (\dot{z})	0	1	-0.3871	-0.1
Diffusion (z)	0	0	0	0
Diffusion (\dot{z})	0.9861	0	0	0

4.2 van der Pol oscillator under additive white noise

This section examines the method’s capability to identify nonlinear dynamical systems featuring self-sustained oscillations in the presence of stochastic perturbations. The van der Pol oscillator is perhaps the most clas-

sical and widely studied example. Characterized by a nonlinear damping, it exhibits limit cycle oscillations that persist without external forcing [33]. In the presence of noise, random perturbations drive the trajectories away from the limit cycle, resulting in a stochastic excitation on the RHS of the governing equation.

Owing to its characteristic self-sustained oscillatory behavior and clear physical interpretation, the van der Pol oscillator has long served as an effective reduced-order model in both the physical and biological sciences, e.g., the modeling of vortex-induced vibrations (VIV) of bluff bodies, electrical circuits employing vacuum tubes, and neuronal action potentials [37, 38]. In the context of fluid dynamics, when a fluid flows past a cylinder, the periodic vortex shedding in the wake causes the structure to vibrate in a limit cycle. Such wake dynamics can be effectively modeled by a van der Pol-type oscillator [39, 40]. As the Reynolds number increases, however, small-scale turbulence develops and disrupts vortex shedding, manifesting as noisy perturbations to the oscillator dynamics [41, 43].

The proposed stochastic system identification framework offers a promising approach to infer the formulation of such stochastic forcing terms directly from data. As a first step toward this goal, the present study examines the method’s performance on a simplified van der Pol oscillator subjected to additive white-noise excitation

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0.2(1 - z^2) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0.5 \end{bmatrix} \xi_e. \quad (31)$$

4.2.1 Data acquisition

As self-sustained nonlinear systems exhibit strongly non-Gaussian behavior, with joint probability densities concentrated around a limit cycle rather than a single Gaussian-like peak, the classical cumulant-neglect closure becomes evidently invalid for them. In this example, the required moment data are obtained from Monte Carlo simulations of Eq. (31).

Unlike numerical simulations, a sufficiently large number of repeated experiments or field measurements is hardly possible. The proposed Selective Segmented Sampling (SSS) and Moment Aggregation (MA) strategies are therefore employed to extract moment data from a single long-run simulation. A time history of displacements and velocities is first generated over the interval $0 \leq t \leq 2.5 \times 10^6$ by integrating Eq. (31) using the fourth-order Runge-Kutta method with a time step of 0.05. After discarding the initial transient response ($0 \leq t \leq 50$), the steady-state signal is subdivided into short segments of 50 each, yielding $5 \times 10^4 - 1$ trajectories.

Four moment estimation schemes are then considered: (a) as a benchmark, high-quality moment data are generated from classical Monte Carlo simulations using 5×10^5 independent realizations, each of duration 50, all starting from $z(0) = \dot{z}(0) = 0$, corresponding to the idealized selection criterion of identical initial conditions; (b) the second scheme estimates sample moments from a single long-run signal, using the SSS approach, selecting only those trajectories starting in the first quadrant of the state space, corresponding to roughly one quarter of all segments; (c) the third scheme further improves the accuracy of the SSS-based estimates by applying the MA strategy introduced in Section 3.4; (d) finally, the fourth scheme applies the MA to a shorter signal of length 2.5×10^5 , using the same selection criterion as in (b), which yields approximately $5 \times 10^3/4$ segments.

For each scheme, all moments up to the prescribed truncation order are estimated, yielding 50-long moment time series with a sampling interval of 0.05. Owing to differences in sample size and estimation strategy, the resulting datasets exhibit varying levels of accuracy. The time derivatives of the estimated moments are computed using a second-order central finite-difference scheme. The resulting mean-squared displacements and velocities obtained from the four schemes are shown in Fig. 10. As expected, all estimated

moments display sufficiently long transient evolution before converging to their stationary values, thereby capturing the essential system dynamics.

Figure 10: Comparison of time-series moments for the exact stochastic van der Pol system and the identified models obtained using four moment-estimation schemes: Monte Carlo simulations with identical initial conditions (top left); SSS applied to a long-term signal with positive initial values (top right); MA applied to the same long-term signal (bottom left); and MA applied to a shorter signal with positive initial values (bottom right).

4.2.2 Identification results

The same set-up of the proposed identification algorithm, including function libraries, moment-equation truncation, and optimization procedure, as used in the first example is adopted here. As expected, the exact forms of the drift and diffusion functions are correctly recovered by the proposed method using high-quality moment data from classical Monte Carlo simulations. The identified models are illustrated in Fig. 11 in terms of forward-simulated trajectories and also in Fig. 10 through the corresponding estimated moments.

The identified coefficients are summarized in Table 3.

Figure 11: Comparison of phase portraits for the exact stochastic van der Pol system and the identified models obtained using four moment-estimation schemes: (top left) Monte Carlo simulations with identical initial conditions; (top right) SSS applied to a long-term signal with positive initial values; (bottom left) MA applied to the same long-term signal; and (bottom right) MA applied to a shorter signal with positive initial values.

The algorithm also performs successfully when applied to moment data estimated using the SSS and MA strategies. Remarkably, the MA approach, even when applied to a short signal, accurately recovers the exact model, highlighting its strong robustness for system identification when data availability is particularly limited. The identified model not only accurately reproduces the cubic nonlinear damping, but also correctly captures the additive noise term. This demonstrates that the proposed moment-based identification framework can reliably recover both the underlying deterministic and stochastic components dynamics, even in the presence of strong noise perturbations and with limited measurement data. Notably, even when applied to deterministic systems contaminated by substantial measurement noise, the method can robustly identify

Table 3: Identified sparse coefficients of drift and diffusion functions for stochastic van der Pol system using moments data estimated via classical Monte Carlo simulations, via SSS scheme applied to a long-term signal, via MA scheme applied to a long-term signal, and via MA scheme applied to a shorter signal (functions with thresholded coefficients are omitted here for brevity).

Data source	Function library	1	z	\dot{z}	$z^2\dot{z}$
Monte Carlo	Drift (z)	0	0	0.994	0
	Drift (\dot{z})	0	-0.9925	0.2036	-0.2
	Diffusion (z)	0	0	0	0
	Diffusion (\dot{z})	0.4997	0	0	0
SSS (long signal)	Drift (z)	0	0	0.9988	0
	Drift (\dot{z})	0	-0.9976	0.2042	-0.2006
	Diffusion (z)	0	0	0	0
	Diffusion (\dot{z})	0.4987	0	0	0
MA (long signal)	Drift (z)	0	0	0.9997	0
	Drift (\dot{z})	0	-0.9981	0.2030	-0.2011
	Diffusion (z)	0	0	0	0
	Diffusion (\dot{z})	0.5049	0	0	0
MA (short signal)	Drift (z)	0	0	0.9997	0
	Drift (\dot{z})	0	-0.9983	0.2011	-0.2006
	Diffusion (z)	0	0	0	0
	Diffusion (\dot{z})	0.5050	0	0	0

the correct governing equations without the need for any prior filtering.

In contrast, the model identified using moment data obtained under a mild selection criterion, namely, selecting trajectories with positive initial displacements, which retains approximately one half of all segments, is shown in Fig. 12 and exhibits poor agreement with the true dynamics. Interestingly, although this dataset is statistically accurate, provided with the larger number of selected segments, it offers insufficient information about the transient dynamics, as the segments share nearly stationary-like initial distributions. A trade-off therefore emerges between data quality and identification accuracy: a stricter selection criterion yields longer transient phase but fewer samples, whereas a milder criterion increases the sample size at the cost of reduced transient information and poorer model recovery.

Figure 12: Time-series moments (left) and phase portraits (right) for the exact stochastic van der Pol system and the identified systems (invisible here due to poor identification) using a mild data selection criteria, i.e., selecting positive initial displacements.

4.2.3 Fidelity of moment estimation

To assess the reliability of the proposed data-acquisition strategies, the effects of both signal length, characterized by the total number of subdivided segments, and the segment-selection criterion, characterized by the proportion of the selected initial distribution relative to the stationary one, on system identification performance are systematically investigated. Identification accuracy is quantified using the minimised loss function defined in Eq. (23), as illustrated in Fig. 13, for cases employing either sample moments estimated via SSS or MA-based moments obtained across varying signal lengths and segment-selection criteria. Criterion 1 selects segments whose initial states lie within angular coordinates 0 to $3\pi/4$ in the state space, retaining approximately $3/8$ of all segments; Criterion 2 retains segments with positive initial displacements and velocities, corresponding to roughly one quarter of the segments; Criterion 3 selects segments with initial states between angular coordinates 0 and $\pi/4$, yielding approximately $1/8$ of all segments.

Figure 13: Identification performance quantified by minimised loss function values using sample moments estimated via SSS (left) and MA-based moments (right), evaluated across different segment-selection criteria and signal lengths in terms of the total number of subdivided segments.

The behavior differs markedly between the two subfigures. For identification using sample moments, tightening the segment-selection criterion can improve accuracy, but only when a sufficiently large number of segments is available. For smaller datasets, identification fails for both Criteria 1 and 3, and therefore results are not reported in those regimes. Notably, the minimum number of segments required for successful identification under Criteria 1 and 3 is significantly larger than that for Criterion 2, indicating that Criterion 2 is more robust in data-limited settings. While Criterion 1 may improve moment estimation accuracy by selecting more consistent segments, and Criterion 3 may enhance transient information through more distinct initial distributions, both reduce the effective sample size or introduce imbalance in the available information, thereby limiting robustness.

In contrast, the trends observed in the MA-moment results reveal that tightening the selection criterion does not necessarily lead to a monotonic improvement in identification accuracy. For cases with more than approximately 3×10^3 segments, the accuracy initially improves and reaches an optimal level before deteriorating as the number of retained segments becomes insufficient. This behavior highlights a trade-off between the preservation of transient information and the available sample size, suggesting that an appropriately balanced selection criterion should be determined prior to application, particularly in data-limited scenarios. Moreover, for all selection criteria considered, identification using MA-based moments consistently outperforms that using SSS-based sample moments, as evidenced by markedly lower optimized loss function values. This highlights the superior reliability of the MA approach in enhancing moment estimation accuracy and, consequently, improving system identification.

To further examine the robustness of the proposed data-acquisition strategies, Fig. 14 presents the accuracy of moment estimation, quantified by the loss function evaluated at the exact system parameters, along time series of both SSS-based sample moments and MA-based moments across varying numbers of subdivided segments. For reference, the minimised loss function values evaluated at the identified parameters are also shown. A lower loss function value at the exact parameters, ideally zero, indicates higher-quality moment data. Complementarily, Fig. 15 reports the relative errors of all estimated moments up to the eighth order, measured using the Frobenius norm and referenced against near-exact results obtained from Monte

Carlo simulations with 5×10^5 realizations.

Figure 14: Data quality (left) quantified by loss function evaluated at the exact system parameters along SSS-based sample moments and MA-based moments estimated across varying number of subdivided segments, and its influence on identification performance (right) quantified by minimised loss function values.

Figure 15: Relative errors of moments estimated using the SSS and MA approaches across varying number of subdivided segments, compared with near-exact moments obtained from Monte Carlo simulations with 5×10^5 realizations.

These results clearly demonstrate that MA-based moments achieve substantially higher accuracy than sample moments estimated via SSS alone. Notably, the MA approach attains comparable accuracy using significantly shorter signals: for example, moments estimated from approximately 1×10^2 segments via MA are as accurate as those obtained from SSS using a long-term signal with 5×10^4 segments. This feature is particularly advantageous for practical applications in which acquiring moderately long time-series data

is challenging. As expected, identification accuracy closely follows data quality, with lower loss function values at the exact parameters leading to improved model recovery.

The dashed portions in Fig. 14 (right) indicate regions in which identification fails due to an insufficient number of segments; in these cases, the plotted values represent expected (dummy) trends rather than successful identification outcomes. This observation reveals the existence of a critical minimum number of subdivided segments below which moment-based identification cannot reliably recover the system dynamics. Importantly, owing to its enhanced moment estimation accuracy, the MA approach substantially reduces this requirement, lowering the critical threshold to approximately 2×10^2 segments.

This conclusion is further supported by Fig. 16, which quantifies identification performance in terms of relative errors in forward-simulated displacements over the interval $0 \leq t \leq 50$, compared with the exact system response. Consistent with the moment-based error analysis, the MA-based approach rapidly achieves low simulation errors even when the number of available segments is limited, whereas the SSS-based approach requires significantly more data to attain comparable accuracy.

Figure 16: Identification performance quantified by relative errors in forward-simulated displacements of the identified systems using SSS-based sample moments and MA-based moments across varying number of subdivided segments, relative to the exact system response.

4.3 Lorenz attractor perturbed by additive white noise

To further assess the capability of the proposed framework in identifying higher-dimensional stochastic systems with chaotic dynamics, we consider the Lorenz attractor subjected to additive white noise [63]. Originally developed as a reduced-order model of atmospheric convection, the Lorenz system has become a canonical example of deterministic chaos [35] and has been widely used in studies of nonlinear dynamics, fluid mechanics, and complex systems. Owing to its strong sensitivity to initial conditions and nonlinear coupling among three state variables, it provides a challenging benchmark for stochastic system identification. The governing equations of the stochastic Lorenz system are

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma(y - x) \\ x(\rho - z) - y \\ xy - \beta z \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \theta_1 \\ \theta_2 \\ \theta_3 \end{bmatrix} \xi_e, \quad (32)$$

where the classical parameter values $\sigma = 10$, $\rho = 28$, and $\beta = 8/3$ are adopted. For simplicity, fully correlated additive noises of equal intensity are considered, i.e., $\theta_1 = \theta_2 = \theta_3 = 10$.

As a prerequisite to system identification, transient moments are estimated using the proposed MA strategy from a single long trajectory of the stochastic Lorenz system. Owing to the sensitivity of chaotic dynamics to numerical integration errors, Eq. (32) is integrated using an adaptive fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme with a maximum time step of 0.001 over the interval $0 \leq t \leq 10^6$. Representative trajectories of the deterministic and stochastic Lorenz systems are shown in Fig. 17.

Figure 17: Comparison of trajectories of the deterministic Lorenz attractor (left), exact stochastic Lorenz system (middle), and identified stochastic system (right) for short-time integration from $t = 0$ to $t = 5$ (top) and long-time integration from $t = 0$ to $t = 50$ (bottom). All trajectories are simulated from identical initial conditions and subjected to the same realization of stochastic excitation for direct comparison.

As shown in Fig. 17, additive stochastic forcing accelerates exploration of the state space and promotes transitions between the two lobes of the attractor. Consequently, the transient response statistics converge rapidly toward their stationary values.

Transient moments up to fourth order are estimated from the simulated trajectories using the proposed MA strategy. The resulting mean squared responses are shown in Fig. 18 (lower right). Despite the chaotic nature of the underlying dynamics, the moments converge rapidly toward stationary values. Following the same procedure as in the previous examples, the proposed identification framework is then applied to recover the governing equations from the estimated moments. Figure 18 compares the exact and identified systems in terms of forward simulations and transient moments, while the recovered sparse coefficients are summarized in Table 4.

Figure 18: Comparison of the exact stochastic Lorenz system and the identified system in terms of forward-simulated trajectories and transient moments estimated using the proposed Moment Aggregation (MA) strategy.

Table 4: Sparse coefficients identified for the stochastic Lorenz system using the proposed framework. For reference, coefficients obtained using standard SINDy applied to deterministic Lorenz dynamics contaminated by additive measurement noise of intensity 1 are also reported [12].

Method	Function library	1	x	y	z	xy	xz
Proposed method	Drift (x)	0	-9.992	9.9956	0	0	0
	Drift (y)	0	28.068	-1.0195	0	0	-1.0015
	Drift (z)	0	0	0	-2.6685	1.0009	0
	Diffusion (x)	9.9892	0	0	0	0	0
	Diffusion (y)	10.007	0	0	0	0	0
	Diffusion (z)	10.007	0	0	0	0	0
SINDy	Drift (x)	0	-9.9614	9.9796	0	0	0
	Drift (y)	0	27.5343	-0.8038	0	0	-0.9900
	Drift (z)	0	0	0	-2.6647	1.0003	0

The proposed method successfully identifies both the nonlinear drift terms and the additive diffusion terms of the stochastic Lorenz system, with all dominant coefficients recovered to within 2% of their exact values. Despite the strong stochastic forcing and chaotic dynamics, the identified model accurately reproduces the transient statistical moments of the exact system.

Due to the intrinsic sensitivity of chaotic systems to initial conditions, the identified model is not expected to reproduce individual trajectories over long time intervals. This should not be regarded as a limitation of the identification procedure, since the objective of stochastic system discovery is to infer the underlying governing equations and statistical dynamics rather than predict individual realizations. In this regard, the close agreement between the exact and identified moments shown in Fig. 18 provides strong evidence of successful system recovery.

For reference, Table 4 also reports results obtained using standard SINDy applied to deterministic Lorenz dynamics contaminated by additive measurement noise [12]. Although SINDy successfully recovers the dominant deterministic structure, it does not identify the stochastic forcing terms because such fluctuations are treated as measurement noise rather than intrinsic components of the governing equations. The comparison highlights the fundamentally different objectives of the two approaches: SINDy seeks deterministic governing equations from noisy observations, whereas the present framework identifies both deterministic and stochastic components of the underlying dynamics.

Together with the previous Duffing and van der Pol examples, these results demonstrate that the proposed framework remains effective for nonlinear stochastic systems ranging from low-dimensional oscillators to higher-dimensional chaotic attractors.

4.4 Mathieu equation with parametric white noise

The fourth example demonstrates the capability of the proposed method to identify stochastic systems featuring random parametric excitation by examining a stochastic Mathieu equation subjected to both stiffness-related parametric white noise and external white noise

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -k_0 & -c_0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ \sigma_e & -\sigma_s z \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \xi_e \\ \xi_s \end{bmatrix}, \quad (33)$$

where parameters are chosen as $c_0 = 0.4$, $k_0 = 1$, $\sigma_s = 0.5$, and $\sigma_e = 1$. This stochastic Mathieu-type system is stochastically stable in the second moment because $c_0 k_0 > \sigma_s^2$.

Unlike the additive-only excitations in the previous examples, the state-dependent diffusion term in Eq. (33) introduces quadratic dependencies on the sparse coefficients in moment equations, which can lead to multiple valid identification solutions (later shown in the results). The prescribed stochastic system, given by Eq. (33), yields a closed set of moment equations that can be directly solved without requiring any closure. Moments up to the eighth order are computed over the interval $t = 0 \sim 50$, shown in Fig. 19, and their time derivatives are obtained by substituting the computed moments into the moment equations. In this example, the identification is performed using polynomials up to second order for both the drift and diffusion functions.

The identified systems, represented by phase-plane trajectories and time histories of forward-simulated responses and moments, are illustrated in Fig. 19, and the sparse coefficients are given in Table 5 and Table 6. Interestingly, in addition to the correctly identified model, the optimization occasionally yields fake sparse models (one shown here) that produce identical loss values.

Figure 19: Comparison of time-series moments (top), phase portraits (middle) and time-history displacements (bottom) for the exact stochastic Mathieu system and the correctly identified system (left) together with statistically equivalent system (right).

Table 5: Sparse coefficients identified for the stochastic Mathieu system corresponding to the correct model (functions with thresholded coefficients are omitted here for brevity).

Function library	1	z	\dot{z}
Drift (z)	0	0	1.0
Drift (\dot{z})	0	-1.0	-0.4
Diffusion (z , external noise)	0	0	0
Diffusion (\dot{z} , external noise)	1.0	0	0
Diffusion (z , parametric noise)	0	0	0
Diffusion (\dot{z} , parametric noise)	0	-0.5	0

Table 6: Sparse coefficients identified for a statistically equivalent stochastic Mathieu model obtained from the same identification procedure (functions with thresholded coefficients are omitted here for brevity).

Function library	1	z	\dot{z}
Drift (z)	0	0	1.0
Drift (\dot{z})	0	-1.0	-0.4
Diffusion (z , external noise)	0	0	0
Diffusion (\dot{z} , external noise)	0.9381	-0.1731	0
Diffusion (z , parametric noise)	0	0	0
Diffusion (\dot{z} , parametric noise)	-0.3463	-0.469	0

Apparently, systems with distinct parameters exhibit different time-history responses, however, their moment evolutions, and in fact all their statistical descriptions such as the evolutionary PDF, can be identical. As will be elaborated in Section 5, two distinct nonlinear stochastic systems may indeed share the same moment equations or Fokker-Planck equations, leading to non-unique identification results. Such alternative models should therefore not be interpreted as spurious results but rather as statistically equivalent counterparts that produce identical observable statistics.

5 Uniqueness of identification

As discussed in Section 4.4, the application of the proposed identification method to parametric stochastic systems may yield multiple statistically equivalent sparse models. To further examine the uniqueness property of the proposed method, the stochastic Mathieu system described by Eq. (33) is revisited.

5.1 State-dependent noisy systems

For illustrative purposes, only first-order polynomial is considered in constructing the function library for the diffusion coefficients, giving the sparse representation form

$$\sigma(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ \hat{\sigma}_e + \delta_1 x_1 + \delta_2 x_2 & -\hat{\sigma}_s x_1 + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 x_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (34)$$

where $\hat{\sigma}_e$, $\hat{\sigma}_s$ are the sparse coefficients expected to converge to the true values σ_e , σ_s in Eq. (33), while δ_1 , δ_2 , ϵ_1 , and ϵ_2 denote redundant coefficients intended to be eliminated by the identification algorithm.

The derivation of the corresponding sparse moment equations requires evaluating the quadratic form of the diffusion term with respect to the Hessian matrix, i.e., $\text{Tr}[\boldsymbol{\sigma}^T \nabla^2(x_1^{a_1} x_2^{a_2}) \boldsymbol{\sigma}]$. This operation introduces quadratic dependencies among the sparse coefficients, thereby rendering the global optimization nonconvex, as discussed in Section 3.3. To ensure that the moment equations of the target system and the sparsely represented system are identically equivalent, and thus produce the same moment evolutions, their quadratic forms must satisfy an identity relation

$$\begin{aligned} & [(\hat{\sigma}_e + \delta_1 x_1 + \delta_2 x_2)^2 + (-\hat{\sigma}_s x_1 + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 x_2)^2] a_2 (a_2 - 1) x_1^{a_1} x_2^{a_2 - 2} \\ & \equiv [\sigma_e^2 + \sigma_s^2 x_1^2] a_2 (a_2 - 1) x_1^{a_1} x_2^{a_2 - 2}, \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

resulting in three nontrivial governing equations for the coefficients of monomials of x_1 and x_2

$$\begin{cases} \hat{\sigma}_e^2 + \epsilon_1^2 = \sigma_e^2 \\ \hat{\sigma}_s^2 + \delta_1^2 = \sigma_s^2 \\ \hat{\sigma}_e \delta_1 = \hat{\sigma}_s \epsilon_1 \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

with $\delta_2 = \epsilon_2 = 0$ obtained from the omitted three trivial equations.

Note that the three equations constitute an underdetermined system, where the number of equations is smaller than the number of unknown coefficients (four), thus admitting an infinitude of solutions. For instance, besides the expected solution $\hat{\sigma}_e = \sigma_e$, $\hat{\sigma}_s = \sigma_s$, $\delta_1 = \epsilon_1 = 0$, alternative solutions such as $\hat{\sigma}_e = 0.6\sigma_e$, $\hat{\sigma}_s = 0.6\sigma_s$, $\epsilon_1 = 0.8\sigma_e$, and $\delta_1 = 0.8\sigma_s$ satisfy the same set of equations. Since these parameter sets yield identical moment equations, the proposed moment-equation-driven method will identify them as indistinguishably valid solutions giving the same lowest values of the loss function.

This reveals a non-uniqueness dilemma that once the stochastic dynamics is represented in the space of statistical moments or probability densities, the diffusion function in the underlying SDE can no longer be uniquely recovered. This limitation similarly occurs to methods that infer stochastic systems via the Fokker-Planck equation or estimate FPK parameters through Kramers-Moyal coefficients. A unique identification result can only be obtained if an additional constraint is imposed, e.g., by enforcing the solution with the maximum sparsity (the minimum number of non-zero coefficients). Nevertheless, the true functional form of the diffusion term cannot be discovered without direct observation of the excitation signal.

5.2 Additive noisy systems

In contrast, for systems driven solely by additive noise, the identification is inherently unique, since $(\hat{\sigma}_e + \delta_1 x_1 + \delta_2 x_2)^2 \equiv \sigma_e^2$ admits only the solution $\hat{\sigma}_e = \sigma_e$. Therefore, the uniqueness of identification depends on the nature of the stochastic excitation: it is guaranteed for purely additive noise, but will be lost once multiplicative noise is present. This insight can further serve as a diagnostic criterion: if the identification consistently yields a single unique solution, the system is likely dominated by external excitation, as commonly assumed in deterministic sparse-regression frameworks.

6 Conclusions

Stochastic nonlinear systems are ubiquitous across natural sciences and engineering, arising from inherent uncertainties in real-world phenomena. Yet, their governing equations are often unknown a priori and difficult to derive from first principles, particularly for complex or multi-scale systems. This challenge has motivated growing interest in data-driven modeling approaches that aim to infer parsimonious and interpretable

models directly from observations. In this work, we bridge two previously distinct research directions, namely forward simulation of stochastic vibrations based on moment equations and inverse identification of nonlinear systems via sparse regression, to develop a unified framework for data-driven discovery of nonlinear stochastic systems.

The proposed framework identifies parsimonious Langevin-type stochastic differential equations using response-only data, without requiring access to excitation measurements. The method represents the drift and diffusion functions as sparse linear combinations of candidate basis functions, derives deterministic moment equations up to a prescribed order, and formulates system identification as a sparse nonlinear regression problem in moment space rather than state space. This shift enables identification to be carried out in a low-dimensional, deterministic ordinary differential equation setting while implicitly accounting for stochastic excitations. To address the sensitivity of moment-based approaches to data quality, a practical data-acquisition strategy combining Selective Segmented Sampling with the proposed Moment Aggregation strategy is introduced. By generating and aggregating multiple approximately independent realizations of sample moments through controlled segmentation, the approach significantly enhances moment estimation accuracy from limited data. Furthermore, to handle the nonconvexity induced by the quadratic dependence of moment equations on diffusion coefficients, a two-phase sparse nonlinear regression algorithm is developed to reliably recover globally optimal sparse models.

The effectiveness and robustness of the proposed method are demonstrated through four representative examples spanning a broad range of nonlinear stochastic dynamics: single- and double-well Duffing oscillators, a van der Pol oscillator subjected to additive noise, a stochastic Lorenz system exhibiting chaotic dynamics, and a stochastic Mathieu system with parametric excitation. Across these cases, the framework accurately recovers both deterministic and stochastic components of the governing equations, even under strong stochastic forcing and limited data availability. The results demonstrate the applicability of the proposed approach to systems ranging from low-dimensional nonlinear oscillators to higher-dimensional chaotic attractors. They further highlight the essential role of transient information carried by conditional moments in successful system identification. In particular, the proposed MA strategy achieves comparable inference accuracy to SSS alone using substantially fewer data segments, significantly reducing the minimum signal length required for reliable identification.

An underlying limitation of the method is also identified: for systems driven by multiplicative noise, the diffusion terms may not be uniquely identifiable from moment information alone, leading to multiple statistically equivalent models. This non-uniqueness reflects a deeper theoretical issue shared by Fokker-Planck-based approaches via Kramers-Moyal estimators, namely the absence of a one-to-one mapping from moment or probability evolution to the underlying stochastic differential equation. While additional constraints such as maximum sparsity can be imposed to select a preferred model, uniquely recovering diffusion structures ultimately requires further information about the excitation process. Despite this limitation, moment-equation-based forward method has a long and successful history in stochastic dynamics. By extending this framework to the inverse problem of stochastic system discovery, the proposed methodology opens promising avenues for data-driven modeling of complex stochastic systems, including nonlinear oscillatory, multistable, and chaotic dynamics, particularly in applications where excitation measurements are unavailable or impractical.

A Convergence of sample moments

Consider a long time series that is subdivided, starting from a certain data point, into N short segments of equal length k . Selecting only segments whose initial values are positive will retain approximately one-

quarter of the total segments. Let the number of selected segments be denoted by n_i . For brevity and without loss of generality, we focus on the estimation of instantaneous moments at the initial time, yielding a collection of random samples $\{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{n_i}\}$.

The sample moment of order a , denoted by $\langle X^a \rangle_{n_i}$, can then be interpreted as the sample average of the transformed variables $\{Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_{n_i}\}$, where $Y_j = X_j^a$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n_i$). The random variables Y_j have expected mean $\mu_Y = \mathbb{E}[X^a]$ and finite variance $\sigma_Y^2 = \mathbb{E}[X^{2a}] - (\mathbb{E}[X^a])^2$. By the classical central limit theorem, as $n_i \rightarrow \infty$, the sample average $\langle Y \rangle_{n_i}$ converges in distribution to a normal $\mathcal{N}(\mu_Y, \sigma_Y^2/n_i)$.

B Convergence of MA-based moments

Next, consider shifting the starting point of segmentation along the signal by one data point, thereby generating a new collection of short segments (their initial points) $\{\tilde{X}_1, \tilde{X}_2, \dots, \tilde{X}_{n_j}\}$ of size n_j . This yields a new realization of the sample moment $\langle \tilde{X}^a \rangle_{n_j}$, which is statistically independent of $\langle X^a \rangle_{n_i}$. Repeating this procedure k times produces a sequence of independent sample moments $\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_k\}$, where $Z_i = \langle X^a \rangle_{n_i}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$), $Z_i \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_Y, \sigma_Y^2/n_i)$.

Since the Z_i are independent but not identically distributed, the Lyapunov CLT applies. Defining $s_k^2 = \sum_{i=1}^k (\sigma_Y^2/n_i)$, the normalized sum satisfies

$$\frac{1}{s_k} \sum_{i=1}^k (Z_i - \mu_Y) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(0, 1). \quad (37)$$

Consequently, the arithmetic mean of the sample moments obeys

$$\langle \langle X^a \rangle_n \rangle_k = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k Z_i \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}\left(\mathbb{E}[X^a], \frac{\mathbb{E}[X^{2a}] - (\mathbb{E}[X^a])^2}{k^2} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{1}{n_i}\right). \quad (38)$$

This shows that averaging over multiple realizations of sample moments reduces the variance by a factor proportional to k .

Alternatively, defining normalized sample moments $\tilde{Z}_i = \sqrt{n_i}(\langle Y \rangle_{n_i} - \mu_Y)$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$), one can generate a sequence of independent and identically distributed variables $\{\tilde{Z}_1, \tilde{Z}_2, \dots, \tilde{Z}_k\}$ with zero mean and variance σ_Y^2 . By the classical CLT, the sample mean $\langle \tilde{Z} \rangle_k$ converges in distribution to a normal $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_Y^2/k)$, and thus the sum of \tilde{Z}_i satisfies

$$\sum_{i=1}^k \tilde{Z}_i = \sum_{i=1}^k \sqrt{n_i} \langle Y \rangle_{n_i} - \mu_Y \sum_{i=1}^k \sqrt{n_i} \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(0, k\sigma_Y^2). \quad (39)$$

Rearranging Eq. (39) yields the distribution of the weighted average of sample moments

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \sqrt{n_i} \langle X^a \rangle_{n_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^k \sqrt{n_i}} \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}\left(\mathbb{E}[X^a], (\mathbb{E}[X^{2a}] - (\mathbb{E}[X^a])^2) \frac{k}{(\sum_{i=1}^k \sqrt{n_i})^2}\right). \quad (40)$$

The advantage of the weighted average is that it achieves a smaller variance than the arithmetic mean, namely,

$$\frac{\mathbb{E}[X^{2a}] - (\mathbb{E}[X^a])^2}{k^2} \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} + \dots + \frac{1}{n_k}\right) \geq \frac{k(\mathbb{E}[X^{2a}] - (\mathbb{E}[X^a])^2)}{(\sqrt{n_1} + \sqrt{n_2} + \dots + \sqrt{n_k})^2}. \quad (41)$$

This inequality follows directly from the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} + \cdots + \frac{1}{n_k}\right)(1 + 1 + \cdots + 1) &\geq \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{n_1}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{n_2}} + \cdots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{n_k}}\right)^2 \\ &\geq \frac{k^4}{(\sqrt{n_1} + \sqrt{n_2} + \cdots + \sqrt{n_k})^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

hence

$$\frac{1}{k^2} \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} + \cdots + \frac{1}{n_k}\right) \geq \frac{k}{(\sqrt{n_1} + \sqrt{n_2} + \cdots + \sqrt{n_k})^2} \quad (43)$$

with equality holding if and only if $n_1 = n_2 = \cdots = n_k$.

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